

Academic Freedom in Venezuela: Context, Restrictions and Challenges*

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Abstract

This article aims to analyze the situation regarding academic freedom and autonomy within higher education institutions in Venezuela between 2010-2018, identifying main restrictions, reprisals, threats and challenges. The research is focused on the grounds of international human rights law standards. Likewise, it analyzes the legislative and institutional framework in Venezuela and assesses the compatibility of domestic law and the practice from the branches of the Public Power with international standards on academic freedom and autonomy of higher education institutions. The research identified a restrictive policy against academic freedom and university autonomy in Venezuela, which is made visible through the normative-institutional framework, budget asphyxiation against universities, criminalization of protest and discrimination against professors and university students, the usurpation by ministerial authorities within the competences of the Public Autonomous Universities, the siege of the Judicial Power against universities and generalized practices to intervene higher education institutions. However, the situation has worsened in the context of the complex humanitarian emergency in Venezuela, which comprehensively affects the University as a key institution for democracy and its key actors: professors-researchers and students. Methodologically, the research is document-based. For the analytical process, this research made use of comparison and qualitative strategies. Research interviews with academic experts, faculties-investigators, students, university authorities and human rights advocates, were conducted as sources of credible data.

* Admisión: 27-01-2019 Aceptado: 19/03/2019

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